

Teachers' Intervention Activities: An Input for Project Care (Community Assistance in Reaching Everyone)

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ABSTRACT

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Project CARE (Community Assistance in Reaching Everyone) in the implementation of new normal basic education in the Elementary Schools of Cluster 9, division of Calamba City utilized a narrative qualitative design. The researchers used coding and verbatim to organize and come up with relevant themes from the testimonies of the participants and organized participants' reflections on the pupils' performance and the interventions conducted by the selected teachers in the elementary schools of Cluster 9, Division of Calamba City school year 2022-2023. as to determine the theme immersed with such. The results showed that the intervention used by the respondent affects the recipients of the projects or interventions such as a) home visitation, b) localized videos and c) crafted supplemental activities. The effectiveness of the result was determined through a) quarterly grade, b) distribution and retrieval of the assessment and c) School Programs and Projects (PPAs) involvement.

The study implied that the importance of interventions utilized by the teachers inside the classroom has a positive effect to the pupil's performance. The said intervention formulates a huge impact on the learning of every learner. The study tackles how localized crafted materials help the learners enhance their knowledge, especially in reading and numeracy skills as one of the fundamental skills that pupils learn and considered as life skills.

KEYWORDS:

Intervention Activities, Community, Assistance, Programs, Projects, and Activities (PPAs).

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching and learning are the main functions of education. Teachers have to improve continually the teaching competencies with which to guide student learning, also other related intervening work. Thus, duties and responsibilities of teachers are expected to perform as mandated in the qualification standards (CSC 1995). Working with other school personnel, parents, and community to the total development of students is one of the teacher's duties and responsibility. Indeed, it is congruent to the Education for All Plan 2015 (EFA), urgency response to the learning needs of the youth and adults Thus, it was reflected on DepEd Order no. 39, series of 2016, Basic Education School Research Agenda (BESRA) Key Reform Thrust 2: Teachers raise the

prevailing standards of their profession to meet demands for better learning outcomes. performance of teachers is a critical factor behind learning outcomes attained by students at schools. Moreover, Republic Act (RA) 10533 otherwise known as the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013" popularly known as K-12 Program dated May 15, 2013, emphasizes the community which will be responsible for pupils' education. Also, Republic Act (RA) 9155 "Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001" viewed that to achieve the holistic development of the pupil's teacher must be equipped with skills and knowledge to provide the needs of the 21st century learners. Thus, RA 9155 is curriculum and learning under School –Based Management with which the school heads and teachers should reduce drop-out rates and increase pupils' performance with the alternative used of educational interventions including home visitation, crafting of new instructional materials, conducting parent meetings, and other related-relevant interventions which will support to the holistic development of the 21st century learner. Indeed, Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers, in virtue of the provisions of paragraph (e), Article 11, of R.A. No. 7836, otherwise known as the Philippine Teachers

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Professionalization Act of 1994 and paragraph (a), section 6, P.D. No. 223 teacher must participate in the continuing professional education program and help if duly authorized to seek support for the school as stipulated in DepEd Order 32, series of 2020 or the Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for school year 2021-2022 in the Light of COVID-19 Public Health Emergency.

Research Question

This study aims to find out the teachers' intervention activities and how it affects the pupils' performance in clusters 9 in the division of Calamba City and it aims to answer the following questions:

Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

The framework shows how the community support affects this project/ intervention to learning of the learners. This framework tells learners to serve as primary source of different interventions. Hence, stakeholders, including teachers and professionals, most specially parents played the vital role in the enhancement of learning of the recipients of the project specifically in reading and numeracy skills. More so, all the support of the community and stakeholders serves as a huge help to make this project successful as seen in figure 1

II. METHODOLOGY

This part consists of research design, the research locale, the respondents of the study, instruments to be used in and ethical considerations. The researchers utilized the narrative qualitative research approach to arrive to the main result of the study and to determine the intervention activities of teachers and how it affects the pupils' performance in Southville VI Elementary Schools of Cluster 7, Division of Calamba City school year 2022-2023

Research Design

The study used a narrative qualitative design. The researcher used qualitative research data such as participants testimonies and reflections to determine the intervention activities of teachers and how its affects the pupils' performance in the Southville VI Elementary Schools of Cluster 7, Division of Calamba City school year 2022-2023.

1. What interventions do you use in teaching?
2. How do you do these teaching interventions?
3. Were the interventions you used effective? Why?
4. Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study was conducted within the bounds of Cluster 9 teachers in the division of Calamba City. It only focuses on the intervention activities of teachers in Cluster 9 in the division of Calamba: An Input for Project CARE (Community Assistance in Reaching Everyone). Thus, it is limited to the elementary teachers, in Cluster 7, Division of Calamba City for school year 2022-2023.

Respondents of the Study

The participants of the study were teachers from Southville VI Elementary School in Calamba City. The study was conducted from the third to fourth quarter of the school year 2022-2023. The teachers are selected elementary school teachers who conduct intervention activities consecutively. The participants were identified and selected based on their intervention activities conducted. A total of five (5) teachers were selected and participated in the study. Participants were composed of primary and intermediate level. The participants agreed to utilize the interviewed guide questions.

Research Instrument

An interview guide questions were utilized to select teachers as participants regarding the interventions used in their everyday teaching. The survey was composed of 3 guided interview type questions. The effectiveness of the said interventions was analyzed. Testimonies and reflections of participants were analyzed and transcribed based on the results and effects of the intervention to the recipient's performance. The analysis focused on the effectiveness of the said intervention using localized crafted materials of the teachers in Southville VI Elementary School and the process itself.

Data Gathering

Three sets of data were collected. The first data was based on the testimonies of teachers with regards to the intervention activities conducted. The second set of data came from the

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simulation of interventions conducted by the teachers and the last was its connection to the pupil’s performance and how the intervention activities made by the teacher-participants affect the pupils.

Research Ethics

The school was subjected to a certain ethical issue. All the participants were provided with consent together with the teachers involved in the study. The researchers secured that the collected information from the participants remained confidential and used only according to the purpose, as indicated in the research

III. RESULTS

This chapter details the results of data collection and analysis and report findings concerning the research questions for this study. The results show the teachers’ intervention and its process on how they used and apply the project/ interventions to the identify recipients and how its affects the pupil’s performance.

Theme 1: Intervention Done by the Teachers

CODES	KEY POINTS FROM THE TRANSCRIPT	ID
Intervention used by the teacher	-Touch Me Math -Localized Numeracy Worksheets -Localized Intervention Materials	JA
	-Strengthen Phonemic Awareness -Assessment -Collaboration with Parents -Provide Reading and Writing Task - Peer Tutoring Home Visitation	MI
	-Nanay Ko, Tutor Ko -Manipulatives Materials -MARUNGKO Parent Participation	CA
	-DR. CUBE (Dimensional Reading Cube) -Utilized Technology and Innovative Design -Pictures -Sounding -Syllabication -Simple Phrases -Sentences.	MRD
	-Tiktalk: Linya Mo, Basa Ko -Sige REPEAT -Online or Video Storytelling -Contextualized stories crafted by some teachers of Southville VI ES. -Story Telling of Stakeholders -Poem Recitation -Dialogue -Tongue Twister	MGD

Table 1 shows the responses of the participants of the research on what are the interventions and projects they used in their everyday teaching. The participants indicate the importance of all the interventions. Also, the answer of the participants has similarities that, all the inventions showed fun and learning to the pupils and it is used in reading

enhancement and numeracy. Also, they indicated the localized crafted materials of the teachers as a tool to the interventions. According to the answers of the participants, they give importance to the involvement of parents/ guardian and stakeholders in every project/ intervention done in the classroom.

Theme 2: Process of the Teaching Interventions

CODES	KEY POINTS FROM THE TRANSCRIPT	ID
Process on how to execute the teaching Intervention	-Parent Consent -Localized Materials and Worksheet -Demonstration of touch me math -Giving worksheets to pupils.	JA
	-Use formative and summative assessment. -Constantly communicate with the parents -Provides Reading and Writing tasks for pupils. -Recite the alphabet in order. -Write all the letters of the alphabet.	MI
	-Nanay Ko Tutor Ko -Parent Consent -Conducted Meeting to parents. -Conducted Training to parents and stakeholders. - Provide localized materials and worksheet align with Marungko Approach	CA
	- Parent Consent - Identify the recipients. - Begin with pupils entering the DR> CUBE Facility - Letters in Alphabets was scheduled per session following the Marungko Approach - Session starts with pictures. - Undergo interactive activities inside the cube like sounding, syllabication, simple Phrases and sentences. - Pupils are given take home activities.	MRD
	- Verbal consent via online - Sending Letters to identified storytellers. - Used contextualizes stories. Sige, REPEAT - Identify the Recipient - Used localized reading materials. - It was done every after class (30 mins)	MGD

Table 2 consists of the responses of the participants about the process of the projects and intervention used in everyday teaching. Since every participant used different interventions, they also have different processes, some of the interventions are about reading enhancement and some are about numeracy. However, the responds of the respondent coincide with the answer of asking parent/guardian consent to identify

recipients of the said project/ intervention. Also, the different activities used by the participants to make the intervention successful, it showed that most of the respondents used localized crafted materials of the teachers of SVES. More so, the said projects and interventions were done every day after class, they rendered another 30 minutes to do this project/ intervention to every recipient every day

Theme 3: Effective Interventions

CODES	KEY POINTS FROM THE TRANSCRIPT	ID
Effectiveness of interventions used by the teacher	Touch-Me- Math is effective, it has huge help to learners to easily recognize numbers and corresponding value and easily solve simple addition and subtraction using fingers and popsicle sticks as counters.	JA
	Yes, the interventions used are effective, it enhanced the reading skills, phonemic awareness/ letter sounds as well as understanding number and their value.	MI

	Nanay Ko, Tutor Ko as one of our interventions used by grade 1 pupils is very effective with the use of localized reading materials 90% of their pupils are able to read in Grade 1.	CA
	The interventions being made in DR CUBE are with quality and effective, the team determined the effectiveness through: Improved Reading Score Increased Engagement and Interest Positive feedback from parents, teachers, and students. Through observation of Master teachers Pupils are able to enhance retention and application skills	MRD
	-Yes, this intervention is very effective to learners, In TikTok, different reading genres were infused with the trend activity which brought both learning and fun to learners. -The Sige, REPEAT project was also used as our intervention and it very effective to our learners. It gives confidence of achieving a step higher learning in reading.	MGD

Table 3 talks about how effective interventions are to the recipients; it shows that all the interventions used are effective to all the learners. Also, according to the table above 90% of the recipients enrich their reading skills and improve the learning in numeracy. More so, respondents insist that aside from learning how to read and enhance the numeracy skill, recipients also feel the enjoyment and fun to every intervention handed down. The table above also tackles how the participants determined how effective the intervention used to the learners and it through feedback of parents/ guardian, teachers, and some master teachers, and through assessment to the recipients and monitoring and evaluation to the project proponents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This part discusses the researcher’s recommendation based on the testimonies and narrative of the participants.

1. School administrators may give special recognition to the teachers implementing intervention activities which in the end contributed to the quality performance of the school.
2. Teachers may invite external stakeholders to support the implementation of the intervention activities which aimed at championing the quality of education including tertiary education, on-the-job- trainees teacher and the like.
3. Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) of the school shall be conducted prior, during and after the intervention activities and may standardized the local M&E securing the validation certificate from the division Learning Resource Management and Development System (LRMDS) office.
4. The teacher-proponents of the project may inform the school stakeholders though intervention reports and information dissemination through school parent

meeting or post the result of the project to the school official Facebook page.

5. Teacher-participants may sustain the project, or the interventions conducted and share the project to its nearby schools or divididon-wide.

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